

Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through
Interdisciplinary Practices in Management

E-commerce Users in India

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An Autonomous Institute Under UGC & Shivaji University
College with Potential for Excellence (CPE) - III Phase.

How to cite this paper: Mrs. Arati Ramchandra Magdum "E-commerce Users in India" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Special Issue | Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through Interdisciplinary Practices in Management, March 2019, pp.17-20, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23052.pdf>

IJTSRD23052

ABSTRACT

E-commerce is playing very important role in the economic development of the country. The extension of ecommerce volumes in India is attracting the attention of players around the world. The e-commerce has changed the way business is done in India. People have evolved as one of the most effective instruments of economic transformation. E-commerce sector has been facing so many problems as number of Indian users are increasing rapidly. Today, the Indian people are more aware towards digital medium. Digital medium tools play vital role in their regular life. The main benefits of e-commerce is Niche market dominance. The main challenges of e-commerce are technological disruption, lack of awareness, security issues and no physical presence.

KEYWORDS: Types, Benefits, Challenges, Regulation etc

INTRODUCTION

E-Commerce stands for electronic commerce and caters to exchange of merchandise, services and knowledge via internet. Electronic commerce is quite simply shopping for and marketing merchandise on-line. It includes the whole on-line process of developing, marketing, selling, delivering, serving and paying for merchandise and services. It's doing business on-line. It includes any Endeavour that takes place directly between a business, its partners, or its customers through transmission and digital IP technology. E-Commerce is a modern business methodology that addresses the wants of the organizations, merchants and shoppers to chop costs whereas rising the standard of products and services and increasing the speed of service delivery. India has shown tremendous growth within the E-Commerce section. E-Commerce has become a very important tool for tiny and large businesses worldwide, not solely to sell to customers however conjointly to have interaction them. though the transition from ancient getting to on-line getting was terribly slow at the start in Indian market attributable to less number of net users thanks to lack of net facility and awareness publicly. However currently

things has changed and also the e-commerce business is growing speedily in our country.

Definition of e-commerce-

Electronic e-commerce is the buying and selling of goods and services, or the transmitting of funds or data over an electronic network, primarily the internet. These B to B, B to C, C to C or C to B.

Types of e-commerce-Business-to-business (B2B)-

E-commerce refers to the electronic exchange of merchandise, services or data between businesses instead of between businesses and customers. **Examples-** Embody online directories and products and provide exchange websites that permit businesses to look for products, services and knowledge and to initiate transactions through e-procurement interfaces.

In 2017, Forrester analysis expected that the B2B e-commerce market can high \$1.1 trillion within the U.S. by 2021, accounting for 30% of all B2B sales within the nation.

Business-to-consumer (B2C)-Is that the retail a part of e-commerce on the net. it's once businesses sell product, services or data on to customers. The term was common throughout the dot-com boom of the late Nineties, once on-line retailers and sellers of products were a novelty.

Today, there area unit infinite virtual stores and malls on the net commercialism every kind of commodity. the foremost recognized example of those sites is Amazon, that dominates the B2C market.

Consumer-to-consumer (C2C)-Could be a form of e-commerce within which customers trade product, services and data with one another on-line. These transactions area unit usually conducted through a 3rd party that has an internet platform on that the transactions area unit dispensed.

Online auctions and classified advertisements area unit 2 samples of C2C platforms, with eBay and Craigslist being 2 of the foremost common of those platforms. as a result of eBay could be a business, this way of e-commerce might even be referred to as C2B2C -- consumer-to-business-to-consumer.

Consumer-to-business (C2B) Could be a form of e-commerce within which customers create their product and services out there on-line for firms to bid on and get. this can be the other of the normal commerce model of B2C.

A popular example of a C2C platform could be a market that sells royalty-free pictures, images, media and style parts, like Stock. Another example would be employment board.

Business-to-administration-(B2A) Refers to transactions conducted on-line between firms and public administration or government bodies. several branches of presidency area unit obsessed with e-services or product in a technique or another, particularly once it involves legal documents, registers, Social Security, fiscals and employment. Businesses will provide these electronically. B2A services have full-grown significantly in recent years as investments are created in e-government capabilities.

Consumer-to-administration (C2A)- Refers to transactions conducted on-line between individual customers and public administration or government bodies. the govt. seldom buys product or services from voters, however people oftentimes use electronic means that within the following areas:

- Education -- scattering data, distance learning/online lectures, etc.
- Social Security -- distributing data, creating payments, etc.
- Taxes -- filing tax returns, creating payments, etc.
- Health -- creating appointments, providing data regarding sicknesses, creating health services payments, etc.

Benefits of E commerce-

Starting Associate in Nursing E commerce business has ne'er been easier. Solutions like Shopify and Woo Commerce

enable even the smallest amount tech-savvy people to line up a store.

Gone area unit the times wherever you'd ought to rent a designer and an internet developer to induce your ecommerce company off the bottom.

Nowadays style templates Associate in Nursinggd applications programme systems enable folks to place an ecommerce store along in a very matter of minutes.

As a results of this folks area unit reaping all the advantages that Associate in Nursinggd ecommerce stores needs to supply.

Below area unit seven reasons that's ecommerce such a beautiful to entrepreneurs:

Global Reach - With a physical brick and mortar store you're restricted geographically to reaching solely the close markets. If you have got a store in big apple and need to conjointly sell in New Jersey you'll ought to open a lot of physical locations.

Ecommerce doesn't have this limitation. In fact, you'll sell to anyone, anyplace within the world via an internet ecommerce business.

Always Open - Physical businesses sometimes have restricted hours, however an internet ecommerce search remains "open" twenty four hours on a daily basis, seven days every week, twelve months a year. this is often very convenient for client and an excellent chance for merchants.

Cost Savings - Ecommerce business have considerably lower in operation prices compared with physical retailers. there's no rent, no workers to rent and pay, and extremely very little within the manner of fastened in operation prices. This makes a ecommerce business very competitive on worth, which might increase market share dramatically.

Automated Inventory Management - It's so much easier to automatize inventory management through the utilization of electronic on-line tools and third party vendors. This has been saving ecommerce businesses billions of bucks in inventory and in operation prices.

Inventory management has become terribly subtle to effectively manage your stock effectively across multiple channels. this might be your own store moreover as marketplaces like eBay, Amazon and your own physical store.

Laser Targeted selling - On-line merchants have the flexibility to gather an incredible quantity of client knowledge to make sure they're targeting the proper folks for his or her product.

This lowers the value of client acquisition, and permits ecommerce on-line business to stay very agile. Imagine having the ability to focus on simply males between 18-24 years previous World Health Organization sleep in urban areas. That's optical device targeted selling that you couldn't get with simply having a physical store.

Niche Market Dominance - Due to the lower in operation prices, the flexibility to focus on your precise style of client

moreover because the advantage of world reach that Associate in Nursing ecommerce web site brings, this ensures that your company may be terribly profitable.

Location Independence – Associate in Nursing e-commerce business owner isn't tied to anybody location once running their business. As long as you have got a laptop computer and an online affiliation you're ready to run your ecommerce business.

Challenges of Ecommerce-

Image credits: Matt Chalwell

In theory everything that we have a tendency to mentioned higher than sounds nice, but there inevitably are going to be some challenges after you conceive to enter the globe of e-commerce on your own.

So within the interest of balance we have a tendency to thought we'd gift the potential pitfalls that you simply might encounter throughout the infancy of your ecommerce journey.

Trust: Trust may be a massive word in ecommerce and may be available many various forms.

- Can your potential customers trust you as a company?
- Can they trust that your chosen payment entranceway won't fail them?
- Can they trust that your product area unit of an honest quality?

A trustworthy payment resolution like PayPal will facilitate instill confidence in folks visiting your web site. employing a review system like Trust pilot or registering your web site as a Google trust store area unit many ways to prevent those potential barriers.

Technical issues: If you aren't technologically minded and let's be honest, you don't got to be so as to start out a store, you will run into some problems.

- What happens if your payment resolution stops working?
- Do you have got a data of hypertext mark-up language, CSS or JavaScript to mend cryptography issues?
- If you wished to style a banner or regulate a graphic on your web store, does one have net style experience?

If you can't fix these problems yourself then you will ought to source. as luck would have it ecommerce solutions like Shopify, Woo Commerce and Big Commerce have dedicated services out there to you to assist if these problems arise.

Competitors: Because the initial came upon prices to start out a ecommerce business area unit thus little this is often creating it a saturated market. thus it's vitally vital that you simply do your analysis beforehand and notice your niche.

No physical presence: Though this is often up with time, the very fact that guests cannot see or feel any of your product are often a downfall.

The thanks to get around this could be to:

- Offer free returns
- Add high resolution pictures
- Show customers victimisation your product
- Include videos your product been used
- Include terribly elaborate description of your product

- Put a FAQ section on every product page

Initial spend: The largest challenge with ecommerce is obtaining started and achieving that every one important 1st sale.

In order to try to to that you simply may have to pay some cash so as to create some. Some nice and value effective ways that to induce you started would be

- Google looking campaign
- Website pop-ups for knowledge assortment
- Abandoned cart emails
- Up sell/upgrade bar on your web site
- Give product away to influencers for content (you will establish these with a tool like Buzzsumo)

Regulation-

Foreign e-commerce is subject to rules in India; beneath native law, foreign corporations area unit to serve alone as marketplaces between vendors and their customers, and area unit prohibited from holding inventory within the country. beneath new rules effective one Gregorian calendar month 2019, foreign corporations are going to be prohibited from commercialism any product from vendors that they management or have equity stakes in, and it's prohibited to enter into exclusivity deals between vendors and websites. This regulation is seen as a counter to Amazon and Wal-Mart's influence on the market, that have given smaller traders an obstacle within the market.

Number of digital buyers in India from 2014 to 2020 (in millions)

Year	Digital Buyers in India
2014	54.1
2015	93.4
2016	130.4
2017	180.1
2018	224.1
2019	273.6
2020	329.1

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This timeline displays a forecast of the quantity of digital consumers in India up to 2020, supported factual numbers from 2014 to 2016. In 2020, over 329 million individuals in India area unit expected to shop for product and services on-line, up from 130.4 million in 2016.

Digital buyer penetration in India from 2014 to 2020

Year	Share of Internet users
2014	30.3%
2015	37.3%
2016	43.8%
2017	52.3%
2018	58%
2019	64.4%
2020	70.7%

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This data point offers data on the digital empor penetration in Bharat from 2014 to 2020. In 2016, 43.8% of web users in Bharat had purchased product on-line. In 2019, this figure is predicted to grow to sixty four.4 percent.

Conclusion-

E-Commerce has created the looking simple. The E-Commerce business in Asian nation is growing quickly despites several challenge. E-commerce business is one in every of the most important growing industries in Asian nation at this time. The sale of e-commerce business is anticipated to grow by nearly four times by 2021 than the sales of 2015. This unexampled growth in E-Commerce is

because of increase in sensible phones and net users, 3G/4G net services, awareness publicly, government initiative of medical care, advanced shipping and payment choices, entry of foreign e-business players etc. Government ought to take steps to produce a correct legal framework in order that hurdles within the growth of e-commerce square measure reduced to minimum.

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